

PHOTOCHEMICAL REACTION WITH SOME INORGANIC COLLOIDS AS ACTIVE AGENTS UNDER THE INFLUENCE OF LIGHT IN VARIOUS STATES OF POLARISATION PART XIV. INFLUENCE OF CIRCULARLY POLARISED LIGHT ON PHOTOCHEMICAL REACTIONS WITH PRE-EXCITED COLLOIDS AS PHOTSENSITISERS.

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SECTION A.

In the previous papers of this series, it was observed that the photochemical reactions, which we have studied, are characterised by a considerable induction period. The reacting systems immediately after mixing up were exposed to radiations in a definite state of polarisation and the reaction velocities under the influence of the same radiation were determined after the induction period was over. It was found that in the case of some photo-active sols the reaction velocities for the same intensities of *l*-circularly polarised radiations were greater than those with the corresponding *d*-circularly polarised light. In this section will be described the results of preliminary experiments which were carried out with sols which were exposed to and matured in light of a definite state of polarisation, before being mixed with the other constituents of the reacting system. It has already been shown that if a sol immediately after its preparation is allowed to mature by exposure to radiation for a sufficient length of time and then mixed with the other components of the reaction mixture, the induction period disappears. Such a process we have termed the process of *pre-excitation* and such sols, we shall describe, as *pre-excited* or *pre-activated* sols.

Photochemical Reduction of Tungstic Acid Sol by Glucose (Ref. Part II ; *this Journal*, 1937, p. 519)

TABLE I.

Tungstate = 0.025M. Glucose = 10%. $p_{11} = 1.24$. Temp. = 29.5°. $\lambda = 366\mu\mu$. d (thickness of the reaction cell) = 0.5 cm. I_{abs} = Intensity of absorbed radiations in ergs/cm²/sec. γ = Quantum efficiency.

Sol preactivated in	Reaction carried in	I_{abs} in which the reaction was carried.	$K_0 \times 10^{10}$.	γ .
1. Ordinary light from point source quartz mercury lamp	Ordinary	146	1.17	1.29
2. Do	<i>d</i> -Circularly polarised	113	0.95	1.38
3. Do	<i>l</i> -Circularly ..	113	0.95	1.38
4. <i>l</i> -Circularly polarised	<i>l</i> -Circularly ..	113	0.95	1.38
5. <i>d</i> -Circularly ..	<i>d</i> -Circularly ..	113	0.70	1.01

Photochemical Oxidation of Glucose by Methylene Blue with Ferric Hydroxide Sol as Photosensitiser. (Ref. Part XII, p. 603)

TABLE II.

Sol = 0.0107M. Methylene blue = 50×10^{-6} M. Glucose = 1%. $p_H = 4.8$.
Temp. = 29°.

Nature of light in which the sol was pre-activated.	reaction was carried.	I_{abs} in which the reaction was carried out.	$K_0 \times 10^{11}$.
Sunlight for 5 mins.	Ordinary	2492	3.48
..	l-Circularly polarised	682	1.00
..	d-Circularly polarised	682	0.99

Photochemical Oxidation of Glucose by Hydrogen Peroxide in Acid medium with Tungstic Acid Sol as Photo-catalyst (Banerjee, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 14, 59).

TABLE III.

Glucose = 0.025M. Tungstate = 0.025M. HCl = 0.08N. Temp. = 30°.
 $H_2O_2 = 0.015M$.

Sol pre-activated in	Reaction carried in	I_{abs} .	$K_{unimol} \times 10^6$.
(a) l-Circularly polarised	l-Circularly polarised	480	4.49
(b) d-Circularly polarised	d-Circularly polarised	480	3.38
(c) Ordinary light	d-Circularly polarised	58	1.56
Do	l-Circularly polarised	58	1.56

Photochemical Oxidation of Glucose by Hydrogen Peroxide in Acid medium with Vanadic Acid Sol as Photo-catalyst (Banerjee, *loc. cit.*).

TABLE IV.

Glucose = 0.05M. Vanadate = 0.033M. Acetic acid = 0.018 M. H_2O_2 = 0.01M.
 $p_H = 5.0$. $\lambda = 366\mu\mu$. Temp. = 27°.

Sol pre-excited in	Reaction carried in	I_{abs} in which the reaction was carried out.	$K_0 \times 10^{10}$.
Ordinary light	<i>l</i> -Circularly polarised	526	3.53
"	<i>d</i> -Circularly polarised	"	3.45
<i>l</i> -Circularly polarised	<i>l</i> -Circularly polarised	"	3.39
<i>d</i> -Circularly polarised	<i>d</i> -Circularly polarised	"	2.37

Tables (I—IV) show that *l*-circularly polarised light is under otherwise identical conditions, more efficient than *d*-circularly polarised light, only when light in which the sol is pre-excited and light in which the reaction is carried out is in the same state of circular polarisation.

SECTION B.

Summary of the results on differences in velocities of many photochemical reactions which were observed with the same intensities of light in the two opposite states of circular polarisation, are given in Tables VA, VB, VC, VI and VII. V_l and V_d represent the velocity constants in *l* and *d*-circularly polarised light respectively, I_l , and I_d being the corresponding intensities of absorbed radiation. It should be noted that in these cases, illumination during the long induction period was effected by the same polarised beam which was responsible for the later photochemical action.

In Table VII, V_{ol} represents velocity constant in *l*-circularly polarised light with sol pre-excited in ordinary light, V_{od} , that in *d*-circularly polarised light with sol pre-activated in *l*-circularly polarised light, V_{ll} , that in *l*-circularly polarised light with sol pre-excited in *l*-circularly polarised light, V_{dd} , that in *d*-circularly polarised light with sol pre-excited in *d*-circularly polarised light, I_{ol} , I_{od} , I_{ll} , and I_{dd} being the corresponding intensities of absorbed radiation.

TABLE VA.

General observation— $V_L > V_D$.

The velocity of reaction varies directly as the intensity of absorbed radiation and was calculated after the induction period was over.

(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
Serial No.	Ref. to part of this series.	Comp. of reaction mixture.	V_L / I_L .	V_D / I_D .
1.	II	Tungstic acid + HCHO	$\frac{1.39 \times 10^{-10}}{237}$ = 5.86×10^{-13}	$\frac{0.95 \times 10^{-10}}{237}$ = 4.00×10^{-13}
2.	II	Tungstic acid + glucose	$\frac{0.70 \times 10^{-10}}{237}$ = 2.95×10^{-13}	$\frac{0.40 \times 10^{-10}}{237}$ = 1.69×10^{-13}
3.	II	Tungstic acid + Laevulose	$\frac{0.61 \times 10^{-10}}{180}$ = 3.39×10^{-13}	$\frac{0.40 \times 10^{-10}}{180}$ = 2.22×10^{-13}
4.	II	Tungstic acid + lactic acid	$\frac{1.87 \times 10^{-10}}{195}$ = 9.59×10^{-13}	$\frac{1.28 \times 10^{-10}}{195}$ = 6.56×10^{-13}
5.	II	Tungstic acid + mandelic acid	$\frac{1.22 \times 10^{-10}}{328}$ = 3.71×10^{-13}	$\frac{0.87 \times 10^{-10}}{328}$ = 2.65×10^{-13}
6.	II	Tungstic acid + leucine	$\frac{0.79 \times 10^{-10}}{385}$ = 2.05×10^{-13}	$\frac{0.67 \times 10^{-10}}{385}$ = 1.74×10^{-13}
7.	II	Tungstic acid + Na-hypophosphite	$\frac{1.54 \times 10^{-10}}{192}$ = 8.02×10^{-13}	$\frac{1.34 \times 10^{-10}}{192}$ = 6.97×10^{-13}

TABLE VA (contd.).

(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
	X	Tungstic acid + K-indigo-tetrasul- phonate + glucose	$\frac{0.302 \times 10^{-7}}{1030}$ = 2.93×10^{-11}	$\frac{0.197 \times 10^{-7}}{1030}$ = 1.91×10^{-11}
	XII	Ferric hydroxide sol + methylene blue + glucose	$\frac{1.02 \times 10^{-12}}{682}$ = 1.49×10^{-15}	$\frac{0.93 \times 10^{-12}}{682}$ = 1.36×10^{-15}
10.	(Banerjee, <i>loc. cit.</i>)	Chromic tung- state + glucose + H ₂ O ₂ (with $\lambda/4$ plate)	$\frac{3.32 \times 10^{-10}}{1100}$ = 3.02×10^{-13}	$\frac{2.56 \times 10^{-10}}{1100}$ = 2.33×10^{-13}
		Do (with Fresnel Rhomb)	$\frac{2.89 \times 10^{-10}}{930}$ = 3.11×10^{-13}	$\frac{2.11 \times 10^{-10}}{930}$ = 2.27×10^{-13}

TABLE VB.

General observation - $V_r > V_p$.

The velocity of reaction varies as the square root of absorbed radiation and was recorded after the induction period was over.

Serial No.	Ref. to Part of this series	Comp. of the reaction mixture.	V_r / I_r .	V_p / I_p .
(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
1.	IX	Tungstic acid+ alcohol + iodine	$\frac{1.36 \times 10^{-10}}{\sqrt{310}}$ = 7.71×10^{-13}	$\frac{1.05 \times 10^{-10}}{\sqrt{310}}$ = 5.96×10^{-13}
2.	IX	Tungstic acid + glucose + iodine	$\frac{2.05 \times 10^{-10}}{\sqrt{570}}$ = 8.59×10^{-13}	$\frac{1.74 \times 10^{-10}}{\sqrt{570}}$ = 7.29×10^{-13}

TABLE VB (contd.).

(1)	(2)	(3)	(5)	(4)
3.	Banerjee (loc. cit.)	Tungstic acid + glucose + H ₂ O ₂	$\frac{5.68 \times 10^{-5}}{\sqrt{728}}$ = 2.11×10^{-6}	$\frac{4.21 \times 10^{-5}}{\sqrt{728}}$ = 1.56×10^{-6}
4.	"	Tungstic acid + formaldehyde + H ₂ O ₂	$\frac{0.79 \times 10^{-5}}{\sqrt{158}}$ = 6.29×10^{-7}	$\frac{0.61 \times 10^{-5}}{\sqrt{158}}$ = 4.85×10^{-7}
5.	"	Tungstic acid + laevulose + H ₂ O ₂	$\frac{2.23 \times 10^{-5}}{\sqrt{241}}$ = 1.44×10^{-6}	$\frac{1.98 \times 10^{-5}}{\sqrt{241}}$ = 1.28×10^{-6}
6.	"	Tungstic acid + glucose + H ₂ O ₂ (in presence of FeCl ₃ , 6H ₂ O)	$\frac{4.88 \times 10^{-5}}{\sqrt{360}}$ = 2.57×10^{-6}	$\frac{3.91 \times 10^{-5}}{\sqrt{360}}$ = 3.06×10^{-6}
7.	"	Tungstic acid + glucose + H ₂ O ₂ (in presence of FeSO ₄ , 7H ₂ O)	$\frac{7.06 \times 10^{-5}}{\sqrt{600}}$ = 2.88×10^{-6}	$\frac{5.52 \times 10^{-5}}{\sqrt{600}}$ = 2.25×10^{-6}
8.	"	Tungstic acid + glucose + H ₂ O ₂ (in presence of CuSO ₄ , 7H ₂ O)	$\frac{7.13 \times 10^{-5}}{\sqrt{600}}$ = 2.91×10^{-6}	$\frac{5.75 \times 10^{-5}}{\sqrt{600}}$ = 2.35×10^{-6}
9.	"	Chromic tungstate + glucose + H ₂ O ₂ at 366μ	$\frac{1.69 \times 10^{-5}}{\sqrt{229}}$ = 1.41×10^{-6}	$\frac{1.16 \times 10^{-5}}{\sqrt{229}}$ = 7.68×10^{-7}
10.	"	Vanadic acid sol (from acetic acid) + glucose + H ₂ O ₂	$\frac{2.56 \times 10^{-10}}{\sqrt{307}}$ = 1.46×10^{-11}	$\frac{1.96 \times 10^{-10}}{\sqrt{307}}$ = 1.12×10^{-11}

TABLE Vc.

Observation— $V_L > V_D$.

The velocity constant is neither proportional to the intensity of absorbed radiation nor to the square root of absorbed radiation.

Serial No.	Ref. to Part of this series.	Comp. of the reaction mixture.	V_L / I_L .	V_L / I_D .
(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
1	IV	Vanadic acid sol (from HCl) + alcohol	$\frac{0.90 \times 10^{-10}}{560}$ = 1.61×10^{-13}	$\frac{0.58 \times 10^{-10}}{560}$ = 1.04×10^{-13}

TABLE VI.

General observation— $V_L = V_D$.

The velocity of reaction is proportional to intensity of radiation absorbed.

(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
1	IV	Molybdic acid + HCHO	$\frac{0.067 \times 10^{-9}}{76.8}$ = 8.72×10^{-13}	$\frac{0.066 \times 10^{-9}}{76.8}$ = 8.59×10^{-13}
2	IV	Molybdic acid + glucose	$\frac{0.052 \times 10^{-9}}{76.8}$ = 6.70×10^{-13}	$\frac{0.051 \times 10^{-9}}{76.8}$ = 6.64×10^{-13}
3	IV	Molybdic acid + alcohol	$\frac{0.018 \times 10^{-9}}{109.8}$ = 1.64×10^{-13}	$\frac{0.017 \times 10^{-9}}{109.8}$ = 1.55×10^{-13}

TABLE VI (contd.).

(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
4	IV	Molybdic acid + leucine	$\frac{0.118 \times 10^{-9}}{433}$ = 2.73×10^{-13}	$\frac{0.116 \times 10^{-9}}{433}$ = 2.68×10^{-13}
5	VII	Uranic acid sol + sodium tartrate	$\frac{0.157 \times 10^{-8}}{300}$ = 5.23×10^{-10}	$\frac{0.165 \times 10^{-8}}{300}$ = 5.5×10^{-10}
6	XI	Uranic acid sol + glucose + methylene blue	$\frac{0.350 \times 10^{-10}}{220}$ = 1.59×10^{-13}	$\frac{0.350 \times 10^{-10}}{220}$ = 1.59×10^{-13}
7	Banerjee (loc. cit.)	Chromic hydro- xide + glucose + H ₂ O ₂	$\frac{3.65 \times 10^{-5}}{229}$ = 1.59×10^{-7}	$\frac{3.56 \times 10^{-5}}{229}$ = 1.55×10^{-7}
8	„	Molybdic acid sol + ethyl alcohol + H ₂ O ₂	$\frac{1.76 \times 10^{-10}}{252.4}$ = 0.69×10^{-12}	$\frac{1.76 \times 10^{-10}}{252.4}$ = 0.69×10^{-12}

TABLE VII.

Serial No.	Ref. to Part of this series.	Comp. of reaction mixture.	$V_D/I_{op.}$	$V_{ol.}/I_{oc.}$	$V_{DD}/I_{DD.}$	$V_{LL}/I_{LL.}$
(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)
I.	II	Tungstic acid + glucose	$\frac{0.95 \times 10^{-10}}{113}$ = 0.84×10^{-12}	$\frac{0.95 \times 10^{-10}}{113}$ = 0.84×10^{-12}	$\frac{0.70 \times 10^{-10}}{113}$ = 0.62×10^{-12}	$\frac{0.95 \times 10^{-10}}{113}$ = 0.84×10^{-12}

TABLE VII (contd.).

(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)
2.	XII	Ferric hydroxide + Me-blue + glucose	$\frac{0.99 \times 10^{-10}}{682}$	$\frac{1.00 \times 10^{-10}}{682}$	...	...
			=	=		
			0.145×10^{-14}	0.147×10^{-14}		
3.	Banerjee (loc. cit.)	Tungstic acid + glucose + H ₂ O ₂	$\frac{1.56 \times 10^{-5}}{\sqrt{58}}$	$\frac{1.56 \times 10^{-5}}{\sqrt{58}}$	$\frac{3.38 \times 10^{-5}}{\sqrt{480}}$	$\frac{4.49 \times 10^{-5}}{\sqrt{480}}$
			=	=	=	=
			0.206×10^{-5}	0.206×10^{-5}	0.154×10^{-5}	0.204×10^{-5}
4.	„	Vanadic acid + alcohol + H ₂ O ₂	$\frac{3.45 \times 10^{-10}}{\sqrt{526}}$	$\frac{3.53 \times 10^{-10}}{\sqrt{526}}$	$\frac{2.37 \times 10^{-10}}{\sqrt{526}}$	$\frac{3.39 \times 10^{-10}}{\sqrt{526}}$
			=	=	=	=
			0.15×10^{-10}	0.154×10^{-10}	0.103×10^{-10}	0.147×10^{-10}

A few important conclusions may be drawn as a result of these investigations on the photochemical activity of sols.

The following sols did not exhibit any circular dichroism when they were exposed to *d*- or *l*-circularly polarised radiations which they are capable of absorbing during the process of aggregation of constituent molecules and ions, to form micelles :—

Molybdic acid, uranic acid and chromic hydroxide. Exposure of photo-active systems containing these sols to *d*- or *l*-circularly polarised light of the same intensity, gave velocity constants of chemical reactions which are always the same.

Sols of tungstic acid, chromic tungstate and vanadic acid behave differently. They do not exhibit circular dichroism when during aggregate formation they are subjected to unpolarised radiation which they can absorb; but when they are exposed to *d*- or *l*-circularly polarised light during aggregate formation, they show pronounced circular dichroism. These are also the sols, which under certain conditions show differential velocities for the same intensity of oppositely circularly polarised radiation, when they form part of a photo-active system. The photosensitive micelles may be formed in (a) the reaction mixture containing the sol forming constituents

by absorption of radiation during the long period of induction, or in (b) the pure sol by long exposure to similar radiations. The pre-activated sol formed in the latter case, does not show any induction period when they form part of a reacting photochemical system. If during the induction period or the process of pre-activation, the system is exposed to unpolarised radiations, and then for chemical reaction, it is exposed to *d*- or *l*-circularly polarised light, no differential velocity of reaction is observed. But if the system is exposed to *d*- or *l*-circularly polarised light during the period of induction or pre-activation, and then the reaction is carried in the same circularly polarised light, it is observed that the velocities are greater for *l*-circularly polarised light than for *d*-circularly polarised light. The sol systems which show this differential effect are known to contain particles which are microcrystalline in structure. It is probable that circularly polarised light exercises a directive influence during the process of formation of these microcrystalline photo-active aggregates, and develops an anisotropic lattice structure. This anisotropy manifests itself as circular dichroism and as a differential velocity effect in photochemical reactions under the influence of circularly polarised radiations. When nonpolarised light is used for the development of photo-active aggregates, neither circular dichroism, nor its differential velocity effect is observed, which indicates that the microcrystalline patterns formed under such conditions are isotropic.

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